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DEPARTMENT OF GEOGRAPHY, TOURISM AND HOTEL MANAGEMENT

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STRENGTH 2024

**STRENGTHENING SUSTAINABILITY COMMUNICATION IN TOURISM,
HOSPITALITY, AND EVENT INDUSTRIES**

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Book of Abstracts

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Novi Sad, August 2024

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EVEN INDUSTRIES

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Micro-Green Framework: Conceptualizing Green Skills Development Through Microlearning in the Workplace

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Abstract: Green skills are increasingly shaping the modern workplace, impacting everything from innovation and efficiency to regulatory compliance and corporate reputation. Equipping employees with skills related to environmental sustainability enables businesses to align operations with societal and environmental values. Despite considerable efforts, the widespread adoption of green skills faces limitations. One key challenge lies in the availability of comprehensive training programs and educational initiatives tailored to the needs of various industries and sectors. There may also be resistance to change and a lack of awareness among employers and employees regarding the importance and potential benefits of integrating green practices into their work. As seen from the GreenComp framework, green skills encompass more than just technical know-how; they involve adopting a greener lifestyle that influences companies. Therefore, to effectively drive change toward a green transition, this paper conceptualizes the development of green skills in the workplace by embracing GreenComp through microlearning experiences across different economic sectors. The framework envisions a unique adaptation of the EU GreenComp framework for four distinct industry sectors (from primary to tertiary). It suggests tailoring content and learning objectives to specific industries, ensuring relevance and applicability, and maximizing impact on the workforce. The inclusion of four different sectors broadens the framework's reach and addresses the diverse needs of various industries. Additionally, by delivering content in bite-sized modules through a microlearning approach, the framework envisions engaging workers in learning activities without significantly disrupting their workflow. This approach acknowledges the time constraints of modern workplaces while still fostering continuous skill development. The paper concludes with recommendations for further practical and theoretical research.

Keywords: Green Skills; Microlearning; Workforce; Green Transition.

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